

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGY ON TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FRAMEWORK.

Olimjonova Gulnoza No'monjon qizi

Guliston davlat universiteti Xorijiy til va adabiyoti yo'nalishi
2-bosqich talabasi.

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Abstract

This article highlights about impact technologies on teaching framework. It shows its benefits to make students memories more reliable to memorise something new. Importantly, it shows its own effect on nature by reducing less handouts.

Key words

ICT, teaching framework, false memories, traditional classroom activities, tools.

Абстракт

В этой статье рассказывается о технологиях воздействия на структуру обучения. Это показывает его преимущества, чтобы сделать воспоминания студентов более надежными, чтобы запомнить что-то новое. Важно отметить, что он показывает свое влияние на природу, уменьшая подачки.

Ключевые слова

ИКТ, система обучения, ложные воспоминания, традиционные классные занятия, инструменты.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola ta'lim tizimiga ta'sir qilish texnologiyalari haqida gapiradi. Bu o'quvchilarning xotiralarini yangi narsalarni yodlash uchun ishonchli qilish uchun uning afzalliklarini ko'rsatadi. Muhimi, tarqatma materiallarni qisqartirish orqali tabiatga o'zining ta'sirini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar

АКТ, o'qitish tizimi, noto'g'ri xotiralar, an'anaviy sinf faoliyati, asboblari.

Technology in the classroom provides foreign language teachers with more tools to support students. In addition to resources like textbooks and worksheets, technology equips educators with various tools to help students develop a better understanding of material.

Furthermore, it saves teachers' time by having a lot of opportunities. They are finding information easily, possibility of being several sources, preparing for lessons beforehand, using prepared materials for a long time, keeping time management, making learning visually, lighting up students' mood by getting catching their attention fully in terms of advanced technologies.

Nowadays, most teachers prefer to use some technologies to conduct their lessons. This process was seen during some period before today with conducting lessons in English. After then, they began using them other subjects such as history, math, literature and etc. Conducting lessons with this kind of technologies gives more confident to foreign language teachers that they can manage to complete all the tasks which they gave. It means progression in students language skills by doing all hometasks.

Use of technologies has several impacts on the way of teaching. Initially, it is known that the way of teaching was simple and based on traditional classroom activities. Traditional classroom activities include some conversation between a teacher and a student. Furthermore, it includes some materials which give to the students to do or learn something visually. Of course, it has its own result in that way of teaching. However, it can not be equal non-traditional one owing to cutting edge technologies. Importantly, using technologies to conduct lessons shows some benefits for nature. Because, teachers use paper to give materials for their students. And then, think about more materials. More materials mean more paper and more deforestation. Using materials can show some positive effects on students but nature.

One of the main point of using ICT in teaching framework is creating an opportunity to students to imagine what they are learning. It is believed that imagination is a key to most difficult tasks which seem to students. However, they will see or watch if they learn something, they can memorise not only on their brain , but also memorise visually. As human memory can be unreliable, and when reaching a sentence with a pragmatic implication, and it leads to false memories. However, imagining a thing which is learned or read can be a great reason of reducing false memorise. To prove the given ideas, it is enough to put Einstein 's quote about imagination: " Imagination is more important than knowledge. Knowledge is limited. Imagination encircles the world.

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